

AN IMPROVED FRAGMENTATION MODEL TO ASSIST THE SELECTION OF FIBRES IN HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

High performance composites used in lightweight structures make use of carbon fibres and a polymer matrix (most often thermosets such as epoxy). Many different efforts have been made to enhance their fracture toughness, at the constituent or at the ply level. Interlaminar toughness has been increased by modifying the matrix with thermoplastic particles. However, intraply fracture of a unidirectional composite involves small deformations and it is essentially brittle.

Fibre hybridization, that is, making use of fibres of different properties, has raised the prospect to escape from brittleness and to achieve a pseudo-ductile behaviour. There have been attempts at different scales: at the laminate scale by mixing plies of different reinforcements, at the ply level by developing fabrics with different fibres, or at the tow/bundle level. This last possibility is particularly appealing because tow hybridization avoids the detrimental stress concentrations found at the other scales, and because the differences in the mechanical properties of the fibres is expected to lead to the best synergetic effect. There are, however, remarkable technological challenges to achieve hybrid tows/bundles.

Currently, however, the decision of which fibres should be mixed, and at which ratio, to achieve a desired mechanical effect is an objective and informed decision. Attempts to base this choice on qualitative arguments has not lead to the best results and the explanation of the positive synergetic effects of hybridization remains a matter of debate. Computational micromechanics will certainly bring light to this topic, but it is a complex and time consuming approach. In this communication we revise an advanced analytical fragmentation model, and illustrate the capability to estimate the tensile response of a unidirectional hybrid composite.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composites can be more damage resistant and thus less brittle if different reinforcements are combined to obtain hybrid configurations.

The hybrid effect have been evidenced by first time in the 70's by Hayashi and collaborators in their study in hybrid composites with unidirectional carbon and glass layers. They have demonstrated an increase in the ultimate strain within carbon fibers hybridized with glass in comparison with the performance of the non-hybrid laminates [1-3]. In the same way, Bunsell and Harris also have reported an increase of the ultimate strain in unidirectional hybrid laminates carbon/glass in contrast with the composites conformed with only carbon. In addition, the hybrid composite have exhibited a gradual failure showing a behavior quite close to the pseudo-ductile response [4]. Furthermore, Manders and Bader [5], have noticed a similar performance in their glass/carbon/glass sandwich hybrids. The pseudo-ductile response obtained by means of hybridization aroused great interest in the scientific community due to powerful applicability of this kind of configurations to be used in structural components. This mix of reinforcements allow to reduce safety factors, minimize the risk of a catastrophic failure, and decrease the weight and cost of the material [6-11].

Notwithstanding that the majority of studies in hybrid materials have been made at macroscopic scale, an improvement of both certain mechanical properties as a progression of the damage of the materials have been reached [8,12-15]. Recent studies have focused their objectives in the improvement of mechanical properties of composites, by mean of hybridization, mixing reinforcements with a kind of fiber in the warp and another one in the weft, or parallel sequential reinforcements tow by tow [16-18]. Others levels of hybridization, this time at microscopic scale, have emerged (intermingled filaments) [6,7], with the purpose of avoid interlayer stress as response of the mix at macroscopic scale obtaining an homogenous material [6,19].

Diao and collaborators [7] have made recently the intermingled hybridization by using carbon and glass fibers (IM7, Hexcel Corporation y T700SC, Toray International Corporation). The random distribution of filaments embedded in poliamide-12 matrix is shown (Fig. 1). Their hybrid composite have shown an improved failure behavior in comparison with the composites made with a unique type of fiber. The material have shown an increased failure strain, retaining the strength (with a little decrease) and the stiffness.

Figure 1: Typical micrograph of the hybrid CF/GF tow [6].

To sum up, the mixture can be done at the macro scale (layers stacked sequentially, woven roving, etc.) or at the micro scale (filaments in a tow). The mechanical properties of hybrid composite materials have been often predicted with the rule of mixtures, considering that the contribution of each component is proportional with its volume fraction.

2 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Fig. 2. Conditions for bundle of fiber and matrix surrounding failed fibers

In tension (assuming that the load increases monotonically), the fibers are subjected to significant fragmentation prior to failure. Besides, the matrix also experiences extensive cracking at moderate stress levels until saturation holding the fibers in place by means of matrix discs (Fig. 2). At the stress levels developed in this context, the distance needed for a fiber to regain its full stress near a break covers several such matrix discs. Around a fiber break, the load is transferred by the matrix, the fiber may slide and recovers its full stress level over a load transfer length L_t , due to the presence of an interfacial shear stress, τ_i , which can be assumed to be constant [20-21].

Since any component made of such a composite contains a very large number of fibers (that pass through each such matrix discs), the overall behavior of the material is described by the averaged value of the individual constituent's behavior. A fiber with a failure within the distance of one transfer length from the disc gives a contribution to the net force acting on the disc. On average, there are approximately the same number of failures on both sides of this disc. Consequently, the contribution from all the fibers to the force acting on the disc tend to cancel out. Furthermore, the net stress over any cross-section of the composite containing sufficiently contributing fibers is obtained from the mean stress in a long (fragmented) fibers subjected to the same strain [20-21].

The only stochastic parameters considered here are the fiber strength (Weibull distributed) and the spatial distribution of the defects (uniform). All the other parameters are held constant, but in reality due to variation in the processing of materials both the fiber stiffness as the diameter are also subject to statistical scatter [20-21]. .

Consider now that the composite is reinforced with two different kind of filaments A and B, uniformly distributed within a tow. The matrix only keeps the fibers in place and redistributes the load around broken fibers via interfacial shear. The geometry and mechanical response of A and B are different, but follow two parameter Weibull distribution: the modulus of Weibull, β , and the characteristic strength, σ_0 , which depends on a characteristic length, L_0 .

The probability of survival for a single fiber of length L at stress σ_f is

$$P_s = \exp \left[- \frac{L}{L_0} \left(\frac{\sigma_f}{\sigma_0} \right)^\beta \right] \quad (1)$$

The mechanical and geometrical features are related with the reference stress, σ_R , which give us an idea of the mechanical resistance of each filament embedded in the matrix that is given by

$$\sigma_R = \sigma_0 \left(\frac{2 \cdot L_0 \cdot \tau_i}{d \cdot \sigma_0} \right)^{\frac{1}{\beta+1}} \quad (2)$$

Here τ_i is the interfacial shear strength and d is the diameter of the fiber,

Considering that this composite is an intermingling of two different reinforcements, each one has a proportion r_A , r_B , that is computed respectively with the following expressions

$$r_A = \frac{V_{FiberA}}{V_{FiberA} + V_{FiberB}} \quad (3)$$

$$r_B = \frac{V_{FiberB}}{V_{FiberA} + V_{FiberB}} \quad (4)$$

With the ratio each reinforcement and following the rule of mixtures the Young modulus of the hybrid composite (neglecting the contribution of the resin) is

$$E = E_A \cdot r_A + E_B \cdot r_B \quad (5)$$

Additionally, it is subjected to an overall strain ε , therefore the stress in the fibers is

$$\sigma_f = \varepsilon \cdot E \quad (6)$$

everywhere except in the recovery zones. Taking a representative cross-section (Fig. 2) the net stress is the sum of all contributions of individual fibers (A and B). The expected value is the average of the each fiber stress over the entire length of fibers subjected to the same strain. The stress recovery contribution, introduced here as a damage variable, can be interpreted as the proportion of fibers subjected to slip if all recovery region were well separated from each other (only for values of w less than one). For each type of fiber this variable can be computed as [20]

$$w_A = \left(\frac{\sigma_{f_A}}{\sigma_{R_A}} \right)^{\beta_A+1} \quad (7)$$

and,

$$w_B = \left(\frac{\sigma_{f_B}}{\sigma_{R_B}} \right)^{\beta_B+1} \quad (8)$$

where

β_A, β_B : Weibull exponents of fibers A and B, respectively,

$\sigma_{f_A}, \sigma_{f_B}$: unimpaired fiber stresses which are used as measure of strain (for instance for fiber A, $\sigma_{f_A} = E_A \cdot \varepsilon$), and

$\sigma_{R_A}, \sigma_{R_B}$: reference stresses introduced in eq. 2.

Accordingly, the macroscopic stress over a cross-section containing a large number of two types of fibers, intermingled and uniformly distributed, can be understood as the participation of two different phenomena: a linear behavior while the fibers are intact and the softening due to progressive failure of fibers. Consequently, the model does not account for local stress concentration.

Taking the Refined Constitutive Model with shadowing and overlapping slip region developed by Neumeister [20], it is possible to include the hybrid effect considering two or more type of reinforcements. In this model, which originally considered only one kind of fiber, the author have defined that all fibers failures occur independently of each other in the specimen. This work have determined also parameters as fraction of fiber length subjected to slip,

$$\lambda = \frac{\sigma_f \cdot d}{2 \cdot L \cdot \tau_i} \quad (9)$$

portion of fibers that can still unaffected after N failures,

$$P_N = (1 - \lambda)^N, \quad (10)$$

or variables as coefficient of failure separation (ratio of length subjected to slip and the maximum length which can be possibly affected by N failures),

$$\gamma = \frac{1 - (1 - \lambda)^N}{\lambda N} \quad (11)$$

For this reason, a stress recovery region is on average overlapped by another region in a fraction $(1 - \lambda)$ of its length. In a slip region symmetrically overlapped to that extent the stress recovers only $\gamma \sigma_f$ over the distance γL_t , thus the mean stress in that recover zone is

$$\overline{\sigma_{sl}} = \frac{\gamma}{2} \sigma_f \quad (12)$$

This expression is the result of an estimation of the average stress in all the slip regions. Now, considering all scenarios the mean stress in all fibers developed by Neumeister is

$$\bar{\sigma}_f = \sigma_f \left[(1 - \lambda)^N + (1 - (1 - \lambda)^N) \frac{(1 - (1 - \lambda)^N)}{2\lambda N} \right] \quad (13)$$

But this expression can be rewritten in function of the damage variable introduced in (7) obtaining the following constitutive relation for an unidirectional reinforced composite with only one type of fiber where the macroscopic stress, σ_∞ , can be computed by mean of the following formula

$$\sigma_\infty = V_f \cdot \sigma_f \left[\frac{1}{w + 1} + \frac{1}{2 \cdot \ln(w + 1)} \left(\frac{w}{w + 1} \right)^2 \right] \quad (14)$$

Here, the term inside the square brackets account for the softening and is close to unity for low values of damage and tends to zero for large strains.

To expand this model to a **hybrid-composite** made with filaments of different nature, it is necessary to include the characteristic of each material and the average mechanical response of the composite. Firstly, is considered the stress of the fibers by using Eq. 5 and 6. Secondly, the corresponding damage variable of each constituent taking into account the damage scenarios explained formerly. As result of this adjust, the model to compute the behavior of the hybrid-composite reinforced with two different fibers, A and B, which is subjected to tension can be computed by using the following expression

$$\sigma_\infty = V_F \cdot E \cdot \varepsilon \left[\left(r_A \left[\frac{1}{w_A + 1} + \frac{1}{2 \cdot \ln(w_A + 1)} \left(\frac{w_A}{w_A + 1} \right)^2 \right] \right) + \left(r_B \left[\frac{1}{w_B + 1} + \frac{1}{2 \cdot \ln(w_B + 1)} \left(\frac{w_B}{w_B + 1} \right)^2 \right] \right) \right] \quad (15)$$

where the terms inside of the first and second parenthesis correspond to the softening of the fiber A and fiber B, respectively.

3. Results and discussions

The new model summed up in Eq. (15) allows to predict the mechanical response of hybrid-composites at early stages of the fragmentation process. With the objective of evaluating its accuracy, the authors have taken as reference the experimental test performed recently by Diao and collaborators, who with the help of an air-assisted fiber tow spreader have produced commingled glass and carbon fiber tows [6]. This technique allows to disperse the filaments within a tow to later combine them, fiber A and B, in a homogeneous hybrid dry reinforcement. Then, the hybrid composite was processed by using resin film infusion (with unidirectional preforms with the commingled fibers). The coupons obtained were evaluated under tension exhibiting a more gradual failure strain (increased by 14%) than the non-hybrid control specimens.

For that purpose we have provided the same properties of components, materials and proportions to our model. The first material is a carbon fiber T700SK-12K manufactured by Torayca™ whereas the second one is an E-glass 5744-735 by AGY™. As matrix, they were used an epoxy resin film HexPly™ M21 from Hexcel. The proportion of mix between the

carbon fiber and glass fiber was $V_{CF}:V_{GF} = 1.55:1$; the volume of fiber (CF + GF) was 0.30. Finally, other geometrical and mechanical data are included in Table 1.

Once used the model, the comparison between analytical and experimental results are shown (Table 2). Finally, the mechanical response and the improvement of a pseudo-ductile curve are also depicted (Fig. 3).

Table 1. Reinforcement data for model validation

Ref.	ID	σ_0	L_0	β	d	E	Ref.
		MPa	mm		μm	GPa	
TORAYCA T700SC-12K	A	2700	100	9.03	6.9	294000	[6,7,23,24]
AGY 5744-735	B	1649	5	3.09	14.9	72000	[6,7,25]

Fig. 3. Tensile stress-strain curves

Table 2. Tensile strength, modulus and strain

	Fragmentation model					Experimental [4]		
	σ_{max} MPa	E^* GPa	ϵ_u %	$\Delta\epsilon_H$ %	$\Delta\sigma_H$ MPa	σ_{max} MPa	E^* GPa	ϵ_u %
CF/Epoxy	1086.3	88.2	1.35	0.40	250.9	1055 ± 167	73.0 ± 8,8	1.34 ± 0.06
GF/Epoxy	501.7	21.6	2.50	-	-	458 ± 14	22.9 ± 0,9	2.34 ± 0.14
Hybrid	849.5	61.6	1.90	1.25	449.5	719 ± 103	51.7 ± 5,0	1.52 ± 0,05

Table 3. Predicted CF mechanical response / Status of fibers

Strain	Stress	Damage, w	Undamaged Fibers (UDF)	Failure Separation and Slipping Fibers (FS-SF)
[mm/mm]	MPa	[]	[%]	[%]
0,0010	88,20	8,88E-13	100,000%	0,000%
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
0,0030	264,60	5,42E-08	100,000%	0,000%
0,0035	308,70	2,54E-07	100,000%	0,000%
0,0040	352,80	9,71E-07	100,000%	0,000%
0,0045	396,90	3,16E-06	100,000%	0,000%
0,0050	441,00	9,10E-06	99,999%	0,000%
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
0,0080	705,24	1,01E-03	99,899%	0,051%
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
0,0130	1.075,67	1,32E-01	88,323%	5,491%
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
0,0105	918,97	1,55E-02	98,472%	0,758%
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
0,0135	1.086,35	1,93E-01	83,819%	7,416%
0,0140	1.085,29	2,78E-01	78,246%	9,645%
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
0,0165	879,56	1,44E+00	40,906%	19,533%
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
0,0195	508,56	7,72E+00	11,472%	18,098%
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮

By using Eq. (14) with the carbon fiber specimen (green line) it is possible to compute both the percentage of fibers unimpaired as the part of reinforced that has suffered separation and/or slipping (Table 3). It can be noticed that under moderate strain levels (0.001 to 0.0045 mm/mm) all the carbon filaments remain intact. As the strain becomes higher, lower quantity of filaments keep undamaged, whereas the first failures begin to appear. Fig. 3 shown that linearity of the

carbon fiber is loosen around 700 MPa and 0.008 mm/mm. This mechanical response correspond to an approximated 99.89% of the intact fibers. By other hand, the predicted strength is equal to 1086.35MPa with a strain of 0.0135 mm/mm. A critical change of the slope is shown between 918 MPa and the maximum stress, with a difference of strains of $0.0140 \text{ mm/mm} - 0.0105 \text{ mm/mm} = 0.0035 \text{ mm/mm}$. This is an important reason due to which this materials are considered brittle. Finally, for large strains (for instance 0.0195), the majority of the fibers have failed (11.472% of fiber keep intact and around 18% with failure separation and/or sliding), phenomena that is evidenced with loss of structural capacity of the material and consequently a poor mechanical response, reflected in a stress of only 508MPa.

A similar analysis can be done considering a hybrid of two different fibers. In this case the model included in the Eq. 15 allow us to overseen how each type of reinforcement contribute to the overall mechanical response, σ_{∞} . With the strain as parameter of control, it is possible to see the amount of stress developed in each group of fibers (carbon or glass) in both individual as global contribution (hybrid effect).

Table 4. Predicted CF/GF Hybrid mechanical response / Status of fibers

Strain [mm/mm]	HYBRID Stress MPa	CARBON FIBER CONTRIBUTION				FIBERGLASS CONTRIBUTION			
		CF Stress MPa	w_{CF} []	(UDF) [%]	(FS-SF) [%]	GF Stress MPa	w_{GF} []	(UDF) [%]	(FS-SF) [%]
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
0.0010	62.08	37.74	2.62E-14	100.000%	0.000%	24.35	2.20E-05	99.998%	0.001%
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
0.0065	399.94	245.29	3.74E-06	100.000%	0.000%	154.65	4.65E-02	95.557%	2.172%
0.0070	429.38	264.15	7.86E-06	99.999%	0.000%	165.22	6.30E-02	94.077%	2.873%
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
0.0190	849.46	659.31	1.76E-01	85.057%	6.898%	190.15	3.74E+00	21.102%	20.005%
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
0.0245	625.64	472.46	2.25E+00	30.770%	20.332%	153.18	1.06E+01	8.638%	17.042%
0.0250	593.88	443.14	2.76E+00	26.629%	20.342%	150.75	1.15E+01	8.008%	16.759%

In this case, as the previous analysis under lower strain the majority of fibers, carbon and glass remain undamaged. Around 0.0065 mm/mm the linearity of the curve is lost starting the degradation of the material. The combination of material expose it maximum stress at 0.0190 mm/mm corresponding to 849.46MPa. In this stage the 85% of the carbon fibers haven't suffer any damage whereas the majority of the glass fiber (around 79%) have contributed with the dissipation of energy providing a gradual degradation of the material. As the previous study, at large strain both materials have suffer lot of damage.

It is important to clarify that the hybrid effect is a tailored mix in which the mechanical properties of a base material can be modified with the purpose to offer a more gradual damage that allow us to prevent a catastrophic/sudden failure. This is obtained sacrificing part of the mechanical properties (-17% of strength) receiving in return a more controlled design space (+40% of maximum strain)

Once evidenced the numerical options to make analysis of the contribution of each material, it is important to evaluate the accurate of the predictions. For the CF/GF hybrid manufactured

by Diao et al, the strength was 1055 ± 167 MPa. This stress was reached at 0.0134 ± 0.0006 mm/mm. By means of the new model the value of the strength is 1086.3MPa, value that is included in the range of variation reported by Diao in his experiments. In this case the corresponding predicted strain was 0.0135 also between the ranges of values that threw the tests. On the other hand, measuring the slope in the curve the predicted Young modulus for the hybrid was 61.6 GPa, whereas the experiments have reported a mean value of 51.7 GPa.

A fragmentation model to predict the behavior of a composite hybrid at microscale level was developed. The hybrid composite exhibited improved tensile failure strain, $\Delta\varepsilon = 0.55\%$ (28% more), compared with the non-hybrid carbon fiber composite, retaining the strength (with a slightly decrease $\Delta\sigma = -236.8$ MPa) and stiffness properties. Therefore, the hardening in the CF-Epoxy was improved from $\Delta\varepsilon_H = 0.4\%$ and $\Delta\sigma_H = 250.9$ MPa to $\Delta\varepsilon_H = 1.25\%$ and $\Delta\sigma_H = 449.9$ MPa offering a more gradual damage in the hybrid composite. To sum up, the combination of materials shows the benefits of the hybridization offering a pseudo-ductile behavior and mitigating the catastrophic failure present in brittle materials.

4. CONCLUSIONS

A new analytical model of fragmentation of fiber to predict the mechanical response of hybrid unidirectional composites under tensile have been developed. This model is based on the refined constitutive model for brittle matrix composites with stress recovery established by Neumeister [20,21]. The model allow to mix and evaluate the contribution of two different kind of reinforcements in an unidirectional-intermingled hybrid showing quantitatively and by mean of the strain, as a variable of control, the conditions of the each type of reinforcement allowing to know what percentage of each one could be undamaged or have suffered failure. In this regard, the main phenomena present during the degradation of the material (failure and slipping) were also exposed. No local concentration of strain are considered in the model.

By using the geometrical and mechanical properties of the materials reported in the literature and that have used to hybridization was possible to predict experimental results of other authors obtaining an adequate correlation between investigational and predicted data.

Further works will be focused in consolidating a robust database with geometrical, mechanical and statistical properties of both, single filaments of different nature, and unidirectional hybrid laminates properly intermingled processed by ourselves.

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